

THE USAGE OF ZEUGMA IN STYLISTIC PERSPECTIVE

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A zeugma is a figure of speech in which a word or phrase joins together two distinct parts of a sentence. There are a few different definitions of zeugma that illustrate the ways in which this figure of speech works. The most common definition of zeugma is a word that is used once, but works in two different ways, such as in the following sentence: "She tossed her hair back and the salad." The word "tossed" in this example has two functions in the sentence. It is a verb in both cases but refers to very different actions. Zeugma can also be as simple as the role of the word "conquered" in the sentence "Lust conquered shame; audacity, fear; madness, reason" (a quote from Cicero). In this case, zeugma refers to the way that the verb does not need to be repeated for it is implied.

I. R. Galperin points out that Zeugma is the use of a word in the same grammatical but different semantic relations to two adjacent words in the context, the semantic relations being, on the one hand, literal, and, on the other, transferred.¹

"Dora, *plunging at once into privileged intimacy and into the middle of the room*". (B. Shaw)

'To plunge' (into the middle of a room) materializes the meaning 'to rush into' or 'enter impetuously'. Here it is used in its concrete, primary, literal meaning; in 'to plunge into privileged intimacy' the word 'plunge' is used in its derivative meaning.

The same can be said of the use of the verbs 'stain' and 'lose' in the following lines from Pope's "The Rape of the Lock":

"...Whether the Nymph
Shall *stain her Honour or her new Brocade*
Or *lose her Heart or necklace* at a Ball".

This stylistic device is particularly favoured in English emotive prose and in poetry. The revival of the original meanings of words must be regarded as an essential quality of any work in the belles-lettres style. A good writer always keeps the chief meanings of words from fading away, provided the meanings are worth being kept fresh and vigorous.

¹I. R. Galperin. Stylistics. Moscow "Higher school" 1977, P.150

Zeugma is a strong and effective device to maintain the purity of the primary meaning when the two meanings clash. By making the two meanings conspicuous in this particular way, each of them stands out clearly. The structure of zeugma

may present variations from the patterns given above. Thus in the sentence:

“...And May’s mother *always stood on her gentility*, and Dot’s mother *never stood on anything but her active little feet*”. (Dickens)

The word ‘stood’ is used twice. This structural variant of zeugma, though producing some slight difference in meaning, does not violate the principle of the stylistic device. It still makes the reader realize that the two meanings of the word ‘stand’ are simultaneously expressed, one primary and the other derivative.

V. A. Kukhareno points out that Zeugma - the context allows to realize two

meanings of the same polysemantic word (or a pair of homonyms) without the repetition of the word itself. ²

From internet recourse alliteration Zeugma (from the Greek: ζεύγμα, zeûgma, meaning “yoke”) is a figure of speech describing the joining of two or more parts of a sentence with a single common verb or noun. ³ A zeugma employs both ellipsis, the omission of words which are easily understood, and parallelism, the balance of several words or phrases. The result is a series of similar phrases joined or yoked together by a common and implied noun or verb. A syllepsis is a particular kind of zeugma, and there is a clear distinction between the two in classical treatises written on the subject. Henry Peacham praises the “delight of the ear” in the use of the zeugma in rhetoric, but stresses that “too many clauses” should be avoided. The zeugma is categorized according to the location and part of speech of the governing word. They are :

Prozeugma

The prozeugma (also called the Synezeugmenon or the Latin praeiunctio) is a zeugma where a verb in the first part of a sentence governs several later clauses in a series.

“Lust conquered shame, audacity fear, madness reason.”

“Povertie hath gotten conquest of thy riches, shame of thy pride, danger of

thy safetie, folly of thy wisdom, weakenesse of thy strength, and time of thy

imagined immortalitie. ” (Henry Peacham)

² V. A. Kukhareno. Seminars in style. Higher School Publishing House Moscow 1971. P.26

³ www.google.com

“Mr. Jones took his coat and his leave”

Mesozeugma

The mesozeugma is a zeugma where a verb in the middle of the sentence governs several parallel clauses on either side.

“What a shame is this, that neither hope of reward, nor feare of reproch could any thing move him, neither the persuasion of his friends, nor the love of his country”. -Peacham

Hypozeugma

The hypozeugma, also called an adjunctio in Latin, is a zeugma where a verb falls at the end of a sentence and governs several parallel clauses that precede it.

“Either with disease or age, physical beauty fades”

“through rain or sleet or dark of night, the mail must get through.” - motto of postal carriers (also contains a rhetorical bracketing and repetition of the word “through”)

“Does not the nightly watch of the Palatine, does not guard of the city, does not the fear of the people, does not the union of all good men, does not the holding of the senate in this most defensible place, do not the looks and faces of these people move you?”

By suspending the verb until the end, the listener is unable to determine what action the atrocities will cause, which is precisely the point Cicero intends to make. In this manner, the hypozeugma lends itself well to the forming of a periodic sentence. Following a hypozeugma with a prozeugma can create a chiasmus.

In many cases an audience will try to second guess the verb that is being suspended. Thus a speaker can subvert the expectation of the listener by deliberately undermining a set-up.

“Family, religion, friendship. These are the three demons you must slay if you wish to succeed in business .” - Mr. Burns, The Simpsons

Diazeugma

The diazeugma is a zeugma where a noun governs two or more verbs. Latin

rhetoricians further divide the diazeugma according to the placement of the subject and verbs.

Diazeugma Disjunction

The subject appears at the beginning of the sentence and each verb follows in its respective clause.

“The Roman people destroyed Numantia, razed Carthage, demolished Corinth, and overthrew Fregella”.

“Physical beauty: with disease it fades; with age it dies”.

Diazeugma Conjunction

The subject appears in the middle of a sentence and may take the place of a conjunction.

“Stands accused, threatens our homes, revels in his crime, this man guilty of burglary asks our forgiveness”.

Hypozeuxis

The Hypozeuxis is the opposite of a zeugma, where each subject has its own verb.

“We shall fight on the beaches. We shall fight on the landing grounds. We

shall fight in the fields, and in the streets, we shall fight in the hills. We shall never

surrender!” - Winston Churchill

Syllepsis

Syllepsis, also known as semantic zeugma, is a particular type of zeugma in which the clauses disagree in either meaning or grammar. The governing word may change meaning with respect to the other words it modifies. This creates a semantic incongruity that is often humorous. Alternatively, a syllepsis may contain a governing word or phrase that does not agree grammatically with one or more of its distributed terms. This is an intentional construction in which rules of grammar

are bent for stylistic effect. Distributed term changes meaning. The governing term can change meaning in its distribution, sometimes to comical effect.

“There's people on the street using guns and knives, taking drugs and each others lives.”

“Yeah she told me she was sick of all the hospital food, and of doctors; distant relatives, draining her blood.”

“Here Thou, great Anna! whom three Realms obey,
Dost sometimes Counsel take - and sometimes Tea”.

Alexander Pope, *The Rape of the Lock* (Pope was speaking of Queen Anne and Kensington Palace; note that in Pope's time, “tea” was pronounced “tay” and thus rhymed with “obey.”)

Syllepsis can be used with idiomatic phrases to achieve a similar result:

“I took her hand and then an aspirin in the morning”,

“She was a thief, you got to believe: she stole my heart and my cat.”

From the film *So I Married an Axe Murderer*

A syllepsis may contain a governing word which does not agree grammatically with one or more of the words or clauses to which it is distributed.

“Loud lightning and thunder shook the temple walls.”

Here, neither “loud” nor “shook” agrees with “lightning”, a purely visual effect.

“The sky - and my hopes - is falling.”

“Our son's diaper - and your excuses - is stinking.”

The first subject is brought to our attention more ominously by the verb with which it agrees.

“You can leave in a taxi. If you can't get a taxi, you can leave in a huff. If that's too soon, you can leave in a minute and a huff”. - Groucho Marx, from Duck Soup

“The levees were broken and so were the promises. - Anderson Cooper”,

Dispatches from the Edge.

The ability to communicate by using words is one thing that sets mankind

apart from all other creatures. God is the author of language.

The figure we are going to cover in this article is Zeugma, which means “yoke” and refers to the fact that two things are yoked together. The English dictionary correctly defines zeugma as occurring when two words or two subjects are controlled by one verb, when lexically and logically the verb fits with only one of the subjects. Zeugma can also occur with parts of speech other than verbs such as when one noun controls two adjectives only one of which is logically appropriate an example of zeugma from Genesis will show us how this figure works.

Zeugma often is a kind of Ellipsis and it is sometimes hard to tell if we should categorize the figure as a zeugma or an Ellipsis. Further more, the print of zeugma is similar to the point Ellipsis in that the words that are actually in the text are emphasized, while the words that are omitted are deemphasized. In the case of Zeugma, the controlling word gets the most emphasis as with ellipsis, when the translators make the decision not to use italic type to show the words they add to the original text.

Who sees with equal eye, as God of all

A hero perish, or a sparrow fall

Atoms or systems into ruin hurled

And now a bubble burst, and now a world

(Alexander Pope, Essay on Man)

Kill all the poys (boys) and luggage

“You are free to execute your lows and your citizens, as you see fit”

(Start Trek: The next Generation)

“He carried a strobe light and the responsibility for the lives of his men”

(Tim O' Brien, The Things They Carried)

But Ted Lavender, who was scared, carried 34 rounds when he was shot and killed

outside Than Khe, and he went down under an exceptional burden, more than 20 pounds of ammunition, plus the flak jacket and helmet and rations and water and

toilet paper and tranquilizers and all the rest, plus an unweighed fear.

(Tim O' Brien, *The Things They Carried*)

"The theme of the Egg Hunt is learning is delightful and delicious - as by the way, am I"

(Alison Ganney as C.G Cregg in the west wing)

"You held your breath and the door for me".

(Alanis Morissette, *Head over Feet*)

Mostkova points out that Zeugma (Gr. 'Yoke') - зевгма use of a word in the same grammatical relation to two adjacent words in the context, one metaphorical and the other literal in sense. ⁴

E. g:

"And the boys took their places and their books". (Dickens)

"Medora took heart, a cheap hall bedroom, and two art lessons a week from professor Angelini". (O. Henry)

"The one martyr who might, perhaps, have paid him a visit and a fee did not show herself ". (A. Bennett)

To sum up, A figure of speech in which a word applies to two others in different senses (e.g., John and his license expired last week) or to two others of which it **semantically** suits only one (e.g., with weeping eyes and hearts)

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⁴ Мосткова. Английская литературоведческая терминология. Издательство "Просвещение" ленинградское отделение ленинград. 1967, Р. 74